

Lower Maastrichtian inoceramid bivalves from the Oslen Krivodol section (Western Fore-Balkan, Bulgaria)

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Abstract. Inoceramid data were used to characterize the lower Maastrichtian strata in the Western Fore-Balkan (Bulgaria), based on the newly discovered Oslen Krivodol section. The upper part of the Kunino Formation yielded a well-defined inoceramid-bearing level. A number of characteristic taxa make up the inoceramid assemblage, including *Cataceramus palliseri* (Douglas, 1942), *C. subcircularis* (Meek, 1876), *C. barabini* (Morton, 1834), *C. glendivensis* Walaszczyk, Cobban and Harries, 2001 and *Endocostea typica* Whitfield, 1880. Additionally, *Trochoceramus* spp. and “*Inoceramus*” sp. were also found. It is, therefore, assumed that both the *Endocostea typica* Zone and an undetermined (probably lower) part of the *Trochoceramus radiosus* inoceramid Zone are present in the section. It is also assumed that there is a mixing of faunas due to low sedimentation rates and local submarine washout.

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INTRODUCTION

The high biostratigraphic resolution of inoceramid bivalves from the upper Campanian–lower Maastrichtian interval has repeatedly been demonstrated to date (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2001, 2002a, b; Walaszczyk, 2004). For the Euramerican biogeographical region, a detailed biostratigraphic inoceramid zonation has been developed, along with an accurate correlation with the conventional ammonite and belemnite zonations in Europe and the Western Interior Basin (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2001, 2002b; Walaszczyk, 2004).

The Maastrichtian Age spans the interval between 72.1 Ma and 66 Ma. The GSSP for the lower boundary of the Maastrichtian was defined in the abandoned quarry at Tercis les Bains (Landes, France) (Odin and Lamaurelle, 2001). The position of the boundary was chosen as an arithmetic mean of 12 bioevents, among them ammonites, inoceramids, dinoflagellate cysts, planktonic and benthic foraminifera, and calcareous nannofossils (*ibid.*). Gale *et al.* (2020) summarized the GSSP of the Campanian/Maastrichtian boundary at 90 cm below the coincident first occurrences (FOs) of *Pachydiscus neubergicus* (von Hauer 1858) and *Hoploscaph-*

ites constrictus (Sowerby, 1817). The FO of the inoceramid species *Endocostea typica* Whitfield, 1880, which has been documented slightly above the Campanian/Maastrichtian boundary (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2001, 2002b), has also been used as a further discriminating bioevent. The occurrence of *E. typica* defines the lowermost Maastrichtian eponymous inoceramid zone, which is stratigraphically followed by either the “*Inoceramus*” *incurvus* and *Trochoceramus radiosus* zones (in the US Western Interior) or the *T. radiosus* Zone (in Europe) of the lower Maastrichtian (*ibid.*).

This paper briefly describes the recently discovered Oslen Krivodol section (Western Fore-Balkan). It is a typical Bulgarian North European-type succession. During the study of the section, characteristic inoceramid bivalves were collected from the upper part of the succession. The section also yielded valuable data on calcareous nannofossils, dinoflagellate cysts and belemnite strontium isotopes, but those will be published separately. This paper presents biostratigraphic results based solely on the inoceramid fauna. Our study is still ongoing; however, based on both strontium isotope evidence and nannofossil data, the Campanian/Maastrichtian (C/M) boundary was drawn at ~3.15 m above the base of the section (Wagreich *et al.*, 2023). Thus, the inoceramid fauna is stratigraphically positioned above the C/M boundary, in the lower Maastrichtian.

GEOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

The Oslen Krivodol section is located at the Western Fore-Balkan, ~1.5 km NNE of Oslen Krivodol Village (Fig. 1). Regionally, the area falls into the Central Balkan–Fore-Balkan Zone of the Balkan orogenic system in Bulgaria (*sensu* Ivanov, 2017). Locally, the section takes part of the Upper Cretaceous strata that crop out along the Iskar River Valley, ESE of the town of Mezdra. In this area, the Upper Cretaceous rocks unconformably overlie medium- to thick-bedded sandstones of the Roman Formation (Aptian). They are covered by different terrigenous-carbonate rocks of Paleogene age.

Section Oslen Krivodol (Fig. 2) is located at the base of a high rock cliff, of which ~6.5 m of sediments were accessible for examination. The lower and middle parts of the section are composed of 3.10-m thick glauconitic limestones to calcareous sandstones that belong to the Darmantsi Formation (uppermost Campanian), while the upper part (3.4 m thick) correspond to thin- to medium-bedded and nodular limestones, with rare interbeds of clayey limestones of the Kunino Formation (lowermost Maastrichtian; cf. Jolkičev, 1986). Above them, nodular limestones of the Mezdra Formation, typically rich in flint nodules, are seen. The latter strata were generally assigned to the lower Maastrichtian (*ibid.*). As far as sequence stratig-

Fig. 1. Geological sketch map of a part of the Western Fore-Balkan (simplified from Tzankov *et al.*, 1994, 1995) showing the study area with the position of the Oslen Krivodol section: 1 – Roman Fm. (Barremian–Aptian); 2 – Kaylaka Fm. (Maastrichtian); 3 – Mezdra Fm. (Maastrichtian); 4 – Kalena, Novachene, Rummyantsevo, Darmantsi and Kunino formations (Santonian–Maastrichtian); 5 – Pavolche Fm. (Lower Eocene); 6 – Ugarchin Fm. (Middle Eocene); 7 – Staropatisa Fm. (Middle Eocene); 8 – Quaternary; 9 – faults; 10 – position of the studied section.

Fig. 2. Stratigraphic log of the Oslen Krivodol section with the position of the inoceramid-bearing level. The Campanian/Maastrichtian boundary was drawn based on strontium isotope and nannofossil data by Wagreich *et al.* (2023).

raphy is concerned, the Darmantsi Formation was accumulated in a Transgressive System Tract and the sea level gradually rose during the latest Campanian. During the early Maastrichtian, the Kunino Formation was being deposited at a still rising sea level, while the Mezdra Formation accumulated within a High System Tract (cf. Stoykova and Ivanov, 2004).

INOCERAMID RECORD

No identifiable inoceramids were recorded in the Darmantsi Formation. At 1.45 m above the base of the formation, a single inoceramid detritic shell layer with belemnite rostra and rare corals was found. The Kunino Formation is devoid of inoceramids in its lowermost beds; however, rare, poorly preserved and indeterminate specimens were observed at ~4.08 m above its base. Our record comes from a single fossiliferous level 5.78 m above the base of the section (lower part of bed 10; see Fig. 2). Inoceramids are mostly medium-sized, but small and large specimens also occur. They are most often preserved as internal molds of single valves, but rare specimens with shells and attached shell fragments were also collected. The inoceramid assemblage mainly consists of representatives of the genus *Cataceramus*, but the genus *Endocostea* is also present. Partially preserved taxa of *Trochoceramus* and “*Inoceramus*” s.l. were also documented. Thus, the inoceramid record corresponds to the following species: *Cataceramus palliseri* (Douglas, 1942) (Figs 3h, i, 4e, 5a–c), *C. subcircularis* (Meek, 1876) (Figs 3f, g, 4c), *C. barabini* (Morton, 1834) (Figs 3d, e, 4f), *C. glendivensis* Walaszczyk, Cobban and Harries 2001 (Fig. 4a, b, d), *Endocostea typica* Whitfield, 1880 (Figs 3a–c, 4g), *Trochoceramus* spp. (Fig. 5d–f), and “*Inoceramus*” sp. (Fig. 5g). It should be noted that the trochoceramids are a common element of the assemblage, but only poorly preserved and fragmentary large-sized specimens were collected, and further study is needed for precise determination.

Based on the FO of *Endocostea typica* in the lower Maastrichtian, Walaszczyk *et al.* (2001)

proposed the *Endocostea typica* Interval Zone in the US Western Interior Basin, with the lower boundary being placed by the FO of the index taxon and the upper boundary marked by the FO of “*Inoceramus*” *incurvus*. The zone is characteristic for the lower part of the lower Maastrichtian and comprises the main change in the inoceramid record in the uppermost Campanian–lowermost Maastrichtian interval (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2001, 2002a). Later, the zone was also established at Tercis-de-Landes, SW France (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2002b) and in Poland (Walaszczyk, 2004; Jurkowska, 2016) (Fig. 6). In Bulgaria, the *E. typica* Zone has been identified in the Bukovets locality (Dochev and Metodiev, 2020), as well as in the Reselets and Kunino sections (Pavlishina *et al.*, 2020) of the Western Fore-Balkan.

The lower part of the zone is characterized by a sudden, often mass, appearance of small-sized *E. typica*, which, however, are not dominant in the mid–upper parts of the zone (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2002b). Other characteristic taxa are *Cataceramus subcircularis* (Meek, 1876) and *C. barabini* (Morton, 1834). A very characteristic species, *Cataceramus glendivensis* Walaszczyk, Cobban and Harries, 2001, occurs in the upper part of the zone (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2001, 2002a, b). In Europe, the *E. typica* Zone lies below the *Trochoceramus radiosus* Range Zone, introduced for the first time in the US Western Interior by Walaszczyk *et al.* (2001). The *T. radiosus* Zone has also been indicated in the Tercis section (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2002b) and KwaZulu (South Africa), as an interval zone (Walaszczyk *et al.* 2009; Fig. 6). The characteristic species for this zone are large trochoceramids represented by the index taxon, as well as by rare *T. tenuiplicatus* (Tzankov, 1981) and *T. helveticus* (Heinz, 1932). The zonal assemblage has distinctive accessory elements, such as “*Inoceramus*” *stephensoni* Walaszczyk, Cobban and Harries, 2001, “*I.* *balchii* Meek and Hayden, 1860, *C. barabini* (Morton, 1834) and *C. subcircularis* (Meek, 1876). In Bulgaria, the *Trochoceramus radiosus* Zone has been proved and indicated in the adjacent Kunino and Darmantsi sections (Pavlishina *et al.*, 2020), and at the Virovsko locality (Dochev and Metodiev, 2020).

Fig. 3. Lower Maastrichtian *Endocostea* and *Cataceramus* specimens from the Oslen Krivodol section (Western Fore-Balkan): *a–c* *Endocostea typica* Whitfield, 1880 (*a* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1815; *b* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1816; *c* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1822); *d, e* *Cataceramus barabini* (Morton, 1834) (*d* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1819; *e* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1824); *f, g* *Cataceramus subcircularis* (Meek, 1876) (*f* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1826; *g* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1817); *h, i* *Cataceramus palliseri* (Douglas, 1942) (*h* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1825; *i* – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1823). All specimens are in reduced size.

Fig. 4. Lower Maastrichtian *Cataceramus* and *Endocostea* specimens from the Oslen Krivodol section (Western Fore-Balkan): a, b, d) *Cataceramus glendivensis* Walaszczyk, Cobban and Harris, 2001 (a – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1820; b – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1834; d – Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1832); c) *Cataceramus subcircularis* (Meek, 1876) (Inv.-Nr. U.S.K₂ 1835); e) *Cataceramus palliseri* (Douglas, 1942) (Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1827); f) *Cataceramus barabini* (Morton, 1834) (Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1836); g) *Endocostea typica* Whitfield, 1880 (Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1833). All specimens are in reduced size.

Fig. 5. Lower Maastrichtian *Cataceramus*, *Trochoceramus* and “*Inoceramus*” specimens from the Oslen Krivodol section (Western Fore-Balkan): *a–c* *Cataceramus palliseri* (Douglas, 1942) (Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1828); *d–f* *Trochoceramus* spp. (Inv.-Nrs. U.S., K₂ 1818; U.S., K₂ 1821; U.S., K₂ 1837); *g* “*Inoceramus*” sp. (Inv.-Nr. U.S., K₂ 1829). All specimens are in reduced size.

Stage	Substage	Ammonite zones		Inoceramid zones				Stage	Substage
		Europe	US Western Interior	US Western Interior	Tercis	this paper	Vistula section (Boreal)		
MAASTRICHTIAN	LOWER (PARS.)	<i>Pachydiscus neubergicus</i>	<i>Baculites grandis</i>	<i>Trochoceras radiosus</i>	<i>Trochoceras radiosus</i>	Oslen Krivodol	<i>Endocostea typica</i>	MAASTRICHTIAN	LOWER (PARS.)
			<i>Baculites baculus</i>	<i>"Inoceramus" incurvus</i>	<i>Endocostea typica</i>				
				<i>Endocostea typica</i>					
CAMPANIAN	UPPER (PARS.)	<i>Nostoceras hyatti</i>	<i>Baculites eliasi</i>	<i>"Inoceramus" redbirdensis</i>	<i>"Inoceramus" redbirdensis</i>		<i>"Inoceramus" redbirdensis</i>	MAASTRICHTIAN	LOWER (PARS.)

Fig. 6. Correlation of the uppermost Campanian–lower Maastrichtian inoceramid zonation in the US Western Interior (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2001), Tercis, SW France (Walaszczyk *et al.*, 2002a), and the Vistula River section, Poland (Walaszczyk, 2004), with the standard ammonite zonation in Europe, the US Western Interior (Cobban, 1994) and the stratigraphic position of the inoceramid fauna from this study.

CONCLUDING NOTES

The scarce occurrence of small-sized *Endocostea typica* in the Oslen Krivodol section indicates the upper part of the eponymous inoceramid zone. In addition, the occurrence of *C. glendivensis*, together with *C. barabini* and *C. subcircularis*, also indicates that the *E. typica* Zone is represented by its upper part. Trochoceramids should also be taken into account as age indicators, despite being poorly preserved and fragmentary. These examples indicate that the *T. radiosus* Zone is also present, but it is difficult to determine to what extent. The faunal mixing is probably due to low sedimentation rates, as

confirmed by the nodular texture of the host rocks. Another possible explanation might be a hidden submarine washout and reworking, in which fossils from the upper part of the *E. typica* Zone were mixed with those from the base of the *T. radiosus* Zone.

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